

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: Methods of learning a foreign language, as well as their retention about methods and level of effectiveness. New pedagogical requirements and implemented process analysis.

Key words: games, methods, interactive method, teaching foreign language.

Recently, the status of a foreign language in our society has changed significantly. Knowledge of foreign languages has become a necessity. In the conditions of active development of international relations the value of a graduate in the labor market largely depends on his language skills is determined. To date, education in the field of foreign languages on a global scale policy is aimed at forming communicative competence.

The task of the teacher is for the practical acquisition of the language for each student to create conditions for every student to demonstrate his activity and creativity is to choose such teaching methods that allow. The task of the teacher is different is to activate the student's cognitive activity in the process of teaching languages. In partnership learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, modern pedagogical technologies such as Internet resources to the individual in the educational process helps to implement a focused approach, children abilities, of teaching taking into account their level of learning provides individualization and differentiation. Computer in foreign language classes forms of working with training programs include: learning vocabulary; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; to write to teach; development of grammatical events.

The most popular interactive educational methods in many literatures today "Case-study" (or "Educational cases"), "Blist-survey", "Modeling", "Creative work". It is noted that it is "problematic education". According to the information, interactive education strategies include "Brainstorm", "Boomerang", "Gallery", "Zig-zag", "Zinamazina", "Muzyorar", "Rotastia", "Snowball". Interactive group work in separating interactive educational strategies from the composition of educational methods that the approach to organization is, in a certain sense, comparable to strategic planning based on In fact, these strategies are more interactive education methods, and there are no other differences between them¹

"MENTAL ATTACK" METHOD. This method shows the students' activities during the training provide, encourage them to think freely and think alike release from inertia, collect diverse ideas on a specific topic, as well as at the initial stage of the process of solving creative tasks serves to learn to overcome emerging thoughts.

The main principle and condition of the "Thinking attack" method is each training Absolutely no criticism of the opinion expressed by the participant prohibition is to encourage all kinds of jokes and jokes. The purpose of this is the free participation of students in the training process is to provide. It is up to the teacher to use this method in the educational process it depends on pedagogical skills and breadth of thinking. The number of students is 10-15 when using the "Brainstorming" method, it is advisable not to exceed one person.

Pedagogical technology in its essence with the help of forms, methods and tools is organized and increases the effectiveness of pedagogical activity and between the teacher decides on mutual cooperation. In addition, learning by students ensures the acquisition of

¹ Sanayeva G. Importance and effectiveness of new interactive methods in teaching english. Oriental renaissance: innovative, educational, natural and social sciences

thorough knowledge of subjects. In students forms independent, free and creative thinking skills. Both necessary conditions are created for students to realize their potential. Also, democratic and it is necessary to guarantee the priority of humanitarian ideas.

The role of teaching through various games in teaching English is incomparable. Playing various games during the lesson increases the enthusiasm for learning science in the classroom, encourages passive students to better participate in the lessons, and creates an environment of competition and teamwork among students in the classroom. It also increases students' respect for their teachers. Below are games that serve to increase the effectiveness of teaching during English lessons.

Last Man Standing. This game is a quick game. But it gives readers some time to think. This game encourages cooperative learning, that is, while other students are talking, the rest of the students are thinking of words themselves. You need a ball to play the game. And all students should stand in a circle. You need to choose a topic. For example: Things found in a kitchen, food, profession, etc.

The game starts by throwing the ball to a student. That student says an English word about the topic and throws the ball to the next student. Each student who receives the ball will have to say something about this topic. If they repeat the words they were told or can't find the words within a few seconds, they leave the game and watch the game sitting down. Don't worry, they will still be learning.

You can change this game a little differently. Instead of talking about a topic, each student can talk about a different topic to the next student. For example, you can start the game by saying "say something red". The first student who catches the ball can say "strawberry" and choose a topic to throw the ball to another. This makes the game a bit more complicated, because before the student can think of a word, he must know what subject word he should think of.

Word bingo. This game requires some preparation to play, but it's worth it. Make 4×4 bingo cards and write words in each box. Distribute these to the students (each must be unique) and have the students mark the words as you read the words. The first student to mark the words on the entire page is the winner. There are several types of bingo game. **Picture Bingo:** Use pictures on a bingo card and read the words associated with those pictures. **Synonym Bingo:** Get your students thinking by saying the synonyms on the bingo card. **Antonym Bingo:** Like synonyms, only students will have to look for words that have opposite meanings, not synonyms.

Try these games in your class and be sure to write down how each of them turned out. Your opinion is important for our further research. If you also know an interesting game or method, write it down.

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